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Development of Bioinspired Fatty Acid-Based Coatings for Advancing Sustainable Agricultural Practices

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This research investigates the development of sustainable, superhydrophobic coatings based on fatty acids tailored for agricultural applications. Recently, we have developed a facile solvent-based deposition method using a spraying technique. The choice of solvent is critical in the development of coatings due to its profound impact on the environment, health and safety, and the final properties of the coating. Solvents influence the drying speed, the formation of the coating's microstructure, and the potential toxicity of the process. In this research, we selected ethyl acetate as it is a good alternative, offering a balance between environmental friendliness, effective evaporation rate that aids in forming superhydrophobic surfaces, and poses fewer health risks compared to more toxic alternatives. These characteristics make ethyl acetate a well-suited choice for achieving sustainable and safe agricultural coatings.

Herein, we demonstrate that we successfully formulated fatty acids-based coatings demonstrating contact angles exceeding 150° and low contact angle hysteresis, which are indicative of pronounced hydrophobic properties. These coatings also exhibit excellent thermal and UV stability, ensuring their durability and effective performance under various environmental conditions. To gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between structure and properties that supports the coating's mechanism of action and to further optimize its performance, we are conducting comprehensive characterization studies using techniques such as scanning electron microscopy (SEM), nano-indentation, high-resolution synchrotron X-ray diffraction (HR-XRD), confocal and optical microscopy, and optical tensiometer. These analyses provide insights into the coatings' surface morphology, mechanical properties, crystal structure, and chemical composition.

Overall, this study provides a foundation for developing innovative, eco-friendly superhydrophobic coatings that could significantly improve crop yield and quality, reduce pesticide inputs, and contribute to the transition toward more sustainable agricultural practices.